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**ОРУЖИЕ ИСКУССТВЕННОГО ИНТЕЛЛЕКТА ВЕДЕТ К
РЕКАПИТАЛИЗАЦИИ ЕВРОПЫ И ПОДРЫВАЕТ СТРУКТУРУ НАТО**

**ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE WEAPONS LEAD TO
RECAPITALIZATION OF EUROPE AND UNDERMINE NATO
STRUCTURE**

Аннотация: в настоящей статье анализируются последствия военного прогресса в Европе. Автор отмечает, что система искусственного интеллекта приводит к необходимости реструктуризации военной базы НАТО из-за отсутствия соответствующих регламентов.

Abstract: the present article analyses the effects of military progress in Europe. The author notes that the Artificial Intelligence system leads to the necessity of NATO military basis restructure due to the absence of appropriate regulations.

Ключевые слова: НАТО, военные силы, технический прогресс, оружие искусственного интеллекта, реструктуризация, баланс сил.

Key words: NATO, military forces, technological progress, Artificial Intelligence weapons, restructure, balance of power.

Technological development is unavoidable in the military sphere considering the morality of state. When the power of one country levels a threat against another country's sovereignty, the threatened country enforces actions to equalize its military strength, consequently ushering in a new stage of the arms race. In the XXI century, Artificial Intelligence weapons, such as drones, autonomous planes, and unmanned maritime techniques have been being invented and implemented in military forces. For instance, The Royal Navy tested The Pacific 950 during NATO exercises in Portugal, cooperating with the Portuguese Navy, Belgium, Italy, Poland, the US and Turkey, as well as the NATO Centre for Maritime Research and Experimentation [5]. Similar experiments in the future will possibly spur the arms race among states instead of preserving peace in Europe and its bordered regions. Therefore, it is conceivable that the step that NATO has put forward has advantages and disadvantages in the region.

Although some experts and officials of NATO claim that the organization is not seeking to be weaponized with killer robots, national governments, defense ministries, and non-governmental organizations are advancing formulas and techniques with guns programmed to detect, target, and shoot automatically. Additionally, among member states, controversy has arisen as to whether humanoid soldiers should be deployed or banned. As an illusion, BAE Taranis Drone, an autonomous aircraft with the capability of reaching speeds of more than 700 mph, was developed and tested in the UK [2]. It is reported that the Taranis stealth drone was designed to demonstrate multiple surveillance and combat tasks that would help shape the future of drone design. Tests conducted in the Australian desert have included complete stealth flight and simulated weapons release tests [6]. In the meantime, Germany and France have been pushing forward proposals to restrict machine guns and draw up an international treaty on precise regulations concerning them. German Foreign Minister Heiko Maas, speaking at

the conference "2019. Capturing Technology. Rethinking Arms Control", urged the global community to outlaw manufacturing killer robots. Nevertheless, neither Germany nor France are listed among the active 22 countries called to ban AI weapons. It is noticeable that officials of most regional countries are conscious about the effects of new types of arms in future warfare. If terminators become a reality, the structure of NATO as well as the balance of power in Europe will change. The reason is that modern arms enlarge the gap among member states in terms of their militaries, which leads to a room in a considerably large part of Europe, from Northern Italy and Austria in the West to Romania in the East and from Estonia in the North to Greece, including Turkey in the South. There are several possible scenarios to conquer the room by AI manufacturers in case a robotic army came to existence.

As usual, the United States initially provided NATO members with cognitive weapons under the guise of protecting them from the threat of Eastern powers or fighting against terrorism, at least joint-surveillance-operations. Valerie Insinna and Aaron Mehta reported in 2017 that the United States is actively pursuing a change to a major arms control treaty that would open the door for wider exports of military drones [3]. The list below illustrates states on the threshold of acquiring military drones.

(Copyright: Johanna Polle, MALE-Drone Proliferation in Europe: Assessing the Status Quo Regarding Acquisition, Research and Development, and Employment. Institute for Peace Research and Security Policy at the University of Hamburg. November 2018.)

In its current condition, NATO is pressuring bordered countries and spurring on the arms race. As a result, Russia and Turkey, though its membership in the organization, may be able to develop their own AI weapons to keep the balance. Leaders of NATO can thereby secure the unity and structure of their alliance. Nonetheless, there are a number of shortcomings which are caused by the

distribution and commerce of military drones. For instance, the originators of robotics armies only multiply their competitors as well as magnify the possibility of acquisition of killer robots by terrorist groups.

On the occasion that the United States and the United Kingdom constrict or lessen weapon sales to the other member states in order to protect national interests and supremacy, space from the Russian borders to the coasts of Portugal would be excluded from market competition. When modernized types of military devices are invented, the balance of power along with global and regional order collapses. In the meantime, alliances and organizations cease their existence due to their inadequacy of contemporary international relations. Although NATO leaders' implementation of unmanned machines strengthens themselves, it undermines the unanimity of cooperation. Stability that relies on nuclear missiles is likely to be replaced by the turmoil of Artificial Intelligence techniques and technologies. On that condition, manufacturers especially depict their allies as consumers evaluating disgrace among members. Ironically, external producers of intelligent robots definitely try to win the chance of achieving the confidence of a market purchaser. As an illustration, after conquering the Middle Eastern market, Chinese combat drones reportedly came to Europe for the first time. Serbia is expected to receive of nine Chengdu Pterodactyl-1 (Wing Loong) drones [7]. Although drones produced by Asian power have not crossed NATO borders yet, US experts are worrying about the dramatic rise of Chinese unmanned weapons distribution around the world and their approach to the organization's space.

“More than two years later, China's growing share of the armed drone market is on display. To date, only the United Kingdom, France, and Italy have bought an armed version of the MQ-9 Reaper, while other U.S. allies, including Jordan, are flying Chinese drones, such as the CH-4 [8]” – writes Sharon Weinberger in the Foreign Policy journal.

Secondly and most significantly, Russian power looms over NATO regardless of whether AI machines are shared or not among member states. For example, it is reported that two Poseidon-carrying submarines will enter service

with the Northern Fleet and that the other two will join the Pacific Fleet. Each of the submarines will carry a maximum of eight drones and, therefore, the total number of Poseidons on combat duty may reach 32 vehicles. Poseidon is an underwater drone weapon, armed with a 2-megaton nuclear or conventional payload that can be detonated “thousands of feet” below the surface. This is meant to generate a radioactive tsunami capable of destroying coastal cities and other infrastructure several kilometers inland [1]. The supersonic power of the Eastern neighbor tends to be so impressive to allies that they are beginning to consider buying Russian weapons. Additionally, Russian systems are more suitable for low budget nations. To address the issue, the U.S. State Department has, in the last year, quietly launched a new program known as the European Recapitalization Incentive Program (ERIP), a new tool developed by the U.S. European Command to try to speed up the process of getting allied nations off Russian gear. As envisioned, it targets Albania, Bosnia, Croatia, Greece, North Macedonia, and Slovakia [4].

The situation shows that military basis of NATO requires restructuring, because there is no complete agreement on modern types of armament and their joint implementation. The Artificial Intelligence system is substituting conventional weapons as well as the balance of power based on nuclear missiles. As a result, member states of NATO are divided into three groups:

Producers of killer robots are those who own their projects and experience in the AI drones sphere (the United States with its Marine Corps program, Joint Air-to-Ground Missile (JAGM) missile system and Predators or the United Kingdom with its BAE Taranis system)

States which are capable enough to buy and place new type of weapons into their forces (mainly Western and Northern European states)

Countries with an inadequate budget or operational skills (especially Southern and Central European states)

Admittedly, NATO is a military organization from its root established to oppose the USSR. It is clear that any transformation of military domain

ameliorates its basic structure. Artificial Intelligence robots are undermining conventional systems and rules among allies. In the future either the United States recapitalizes on the military markets of NATO states, or Russia and China will be on the threshold of alleviating the unanimity of the organization though bilateral and multilateral agreements supplemented by cheap and efficient new generation robots.

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